

Impact of land use change on water scarcity in upstream Ciliwung watershed, West Java, Indonesia

Yuliya Mahdalena Hidayat*

Research Center for Water Resources, Research and Development Agency, Ministry of Public Works and Housing. Jalan Ir. H. Juanda 193 Bandung, West Java, Indonesia

*Corresponding author : yuliya96119@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Irrigation plays a role of vital importance in supporting food security in Indonesia. However, land use change in watershed areas stimulates water scarcity. This research aims to study lack of water in some irrigation areas due to land use change and to analyze its adaptation. Source data was secondary data from some stakeholders and routing of literature. The Result indicates that a number of existing irrigation area in Ciliwung often indicates lack of water due to land conversion in the catchment as. Tourism activity and development of tourism infrastructure facilities. Land use changes in upstream was identified by land conversion that decrease land cover and increase human settlement. Based on analysis of upstream Ciliwung watershed AWLR Katulampa, ratio of maximum discharge and minimum discharge (Q_{max}/Q_{min}) is $171.39 > 120$, this means upstream Ciliwung river catchment is indicated in critical catchment. As adaptation step to Water scarcity due to land use change, some irrigation areas are performed to change planting pattern and agricultural methods.

Keywords: *adaptation, irrigation, food security, lacking of water, land use change*

INTRODUCTION

Water is the natural resources that have an important function for human live and being other live. Water is also as an authorized capital in development. The water resources as irrigation in agricultural development take a role of vital importance in supporting food security in Indonesia. Water availability is not quit to irrigate the irrigation areas in increasing food production. On the other hand, according to the character, water always follow the hidrologis cycle related with wheater condition, so that water availability does not flat every time and every region. Development growth in several sectors such as agriculture, plantation, industry, exploitation of the natural resources for mining, and forest exploitation causes degradation of hidrological condition of the watershed that influences to water availability in the watershed.

Land use change on the upstream Ciliwung has degraded water availability in Cibanon irrigation area of watershed. The previous research shows that land use change in the upstream Ciliwung watershed caused

expansion of Puncak areas as a target of the tourism (Pramono, 2010), and expansion of the building area which converts dry upland and paddy field (Ruspendi et al., 2013). An other research also mentions that Ciliwung is one of the critical basin, with the high land conversion whitout environment knowledge (Wahyuni and Syartinilia, 2015).

Land use change caused decrease of the diffusion area on the Ciliwung watershed, degrading water availability, lessening the amount of water required by crop, so that adaptation is needed to continue irrigation systems. The purpose of this research is to study lack of water in some irrigated areas due to land use change and also to analyze its adaptation to continue irrigation systems.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Some materials that used in this research were:

1. The Ciliwung watershed topography map obtained from secondary pursuant to data source data of the BPDAS Ciliwung-Citarum in Swandayani Thesis year 2010.
2. The upstream Ciliwung land use map in year 1990, 2000, and 2011, obtained from secondary data from the Ciliwung watershed land cover map, Badan Planologi Nasional year 2012, that have overlaid with the upstream Ciliwung watershed map with shp extension file. Type of land use are natural forest, plantation forest, mix plantation, build up area, dry land agriculture, paddy field and shrub. Method to differentiate of the each land use by arranging the colour degradadation.
3. Data of irrigation area, discharge of the weir and plant pattern, obtained from Dinas Sumber Daya Air, West Java Province. Discharge of the weir get from year 1993-2017. Plant pattern data obtained from 2 (two) periods are in globally planning of the plant arrangement in year 2010/2011 and in year 2017/2018.
4. Maximum-minimum discharge data of the Ciliwung river based on AWLR Katulampa from 1995-2003, from the secondary data from BBWS Ciliwung Cisadane (Lisnawati and Wibowo, 2010).

Analysis to the data and map, covering pattern plant, discharge degradation in the weir, watershed shape based analysis, land use change, land use change to discharge, and adaptation to water scarcity.

Pattern plant and discharge degradation in the irrigation weir were analyzed based on the secondary data received. Analysis of watershed shape was based on topography map, land use change was analyzed based on land use change in 1990, 2000, 2012 and routing previous literature study. Land use change to discharge was analyzed by river regime coefficient which are

comparison between maximum and minimum discharge, based on Peraturan Menteri Kehutanan no P.61 in 2014. Adaptation to the water scarcity was performed by planting intensity and agricultural methods. Comparison graphs between pledge discharge and operation water required for irrigation can depict period time of the water lacking. Pledge discharge irrigation represents discharge with probability 80%. Water operation required for irrigation represents the number of water required for period I and II of rice planting and period III of secondary planting. Adaptation to the present has made based on several planting intensity scenario, and then has made further by changing agricultural methods.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Plant Pattern

Cibanon irrigation areas of 596 ha cover 559 ha in Bogor sub-province dan 37 ha in Bogor town which have general planting pattern of paddy-paddy-secondary crops. Based on the global planning of the plant arrangement from data of 2011, from irrigation areas of 596 ha are about 510 ha for paddy field.

Discharge Degradation in the Irrigation Weir

Discharge on the Cibanon weir as a water resources for Cibanon irrigation areas have degraded. In period of 1993-1996, water availability in the weir reaches 10 m³/s for maximum number and 1,925 m³/s for minimum one. While over the 2002, there are extreme discharge on 2013 which reach 67,473 m³/s for maximum number and 0 for minimum on the 2009. Then, on 1999, was big floods so that sweep away to barricade. Discharge trend change and floods indicate to be base flow change on the Ciliwung river, base flow tend to downhill from year to year downhill indicating to downhill land infiltration.

Watershed Shape Based Analysis

Cibanon irrigation areas located on the middle of watershed, and sloping area based on topography map (Figure 1.), so that upstream watershed activity have influenced the Cibanon on the middle.

Upstream Ciliwung watershed shape is like semi fan or radial, caused riners input flow concentration to one dot around area of Katulampa/Ciawi. This pattern gives big floods discharge and fluctuative in meeting point of river input, because of time concentration to the river input as relative uniform. Upstream Ciliwung watershed outlet in Katulampa is inlet for middle Ciliwung watershed.

Data Source : Swandayani, 2010

Figure 1. Topographic map of the Ciliwung watershed

Middle Ciliwung watershed covers areas of 13,763 ha, in form of length look like open duct. With this form, condition of topography which tend to slopingly, and additional with the condition of its physical tend is surge, so retardation stream factor in this middle shares enough weaken that river stream and run off passing quickly go to downstream. A highly water to be run off, and at least water come into ground caused base flow decreasing and discharge on the stream become a little when the rain does not happened.

Land Use Change

Development of Puncak areas as a tourism caused increasing pressure to the landfarm resource in upper Ciliwung watershed. Tourism activity in Puncak and increasing of the utility such as roads, shop, villa and hotels enhance land conversion, that the vegetative land change to building area (Pramono, 2010).

Data source : BPLAN, 2012

Figure 2. Land use in the year 1990, 2000 and 2011 of the upstream Ciliwung watershed

Land use change to building areas from 1990 to 2011 has reached 153%, that have being increased the mix plantation, natural forest, dry land

agriculture, shrub dan paddy field. Analysis result showed that most of agricultural uplands are converted to building areas. Previous research showed appearance satellite city by developer (Wasis et al., 2012), build around mains city among others in around Bogor (Arifin, 2011), there are noted 31 estate developers in Bogor (Arifin, 2011).

Previous research showed that there was a quick conversion of state forest and people forest in the upper Ciliwung watershed, that is in Cisarua dan Megamendung district to building areas, namely 225.90 ha per year in 1995-2003 (Pramono, 2010). Image analysis of the land use change map in Puncak areas covering Ciawi, Megamendung and Cisarua showed the same tendency that the widely degradation of forest, tea garden, mixture garden and shrub have been occurred. On the other hand, accelerate of land conversion to building areas is more excelsior (Lisnawati and Wibowo, 2010).

Land use change to discharge

Stream fluctuation discharge among both snappy seasons indicates annoyed function and degradation of the watershed quality. Other research mention that forest conversion to another use was influenced the hydrological characteristics such as discharge degradation in dry season and increasing surface run off in high rainfall (Pratama and Yuwono, 2016).

Existence of the urban building areas addition rapidly in Puncak areas has result of increasing waterproof area, so that lessen infiltration water into ground. If expanding of the building areas are uncontrolable, every high rainfall intensity happened will improve maximum discharge, and when low rainfall minimum discharge will progressively go down. That’s can be shown the fact that rainfall in upstream Ciliwung watershed from 1995-2003 tend to decline, but maximum discharge tend to increase and so do to difference of maximum-minimum discharge (Table 1). This condition indicates that degradation of the upstream Ciliwung watershed can be determined by maximum-minimum discharge ratio.

Table 1. Maximum-minimum Ciliwung river discharge in the AWLR Katulampa

Year	Minimum discharge (m ³ /s)	Maximum discharge (m ³ /s)	Δ Maximum-minimum discharge (m ³ /s)	Ratio of maximum-minimum discharge
1995	1.71	244.20	242.49	142.64
1997	1.22	244.20	242.98	199.51
2001	3.46	411.68	408.22	118.98
2003	1.22	298.73	293.51	224.44
Mean	1.91	293.70	291.80	171.39

Data source: BB244.20WS Ciliwung Cisadane in Lisnawati and Wibowo, 2010

The quality of upstream Ciliwung watershed based on comparison of $Q_{max}/Q_{min} = 171.39$ (in the Bendung weir) is a critical catchment. So, to prevent degradation of the watershed quality furthermore, the remain of land with covered vegetation should be preserved, and expansion of building areas must be depressed.

Adaptation to water scarcity

Water scarcity in the Cibanon weir is occurred because of discharge degradation due to land use change in the upstream Ciliwung watershed as a consequence from increasing population and tourism facilities before reaching to the weir, water have been distributed to other activities, beside the existence of the base flow degradation effect of low infiltration. This difficult situation is true avoided, so adaptation action for this condition is accomodated by planting intensity with discharge availability.

Adaptation scenario was made by 4 (four) wide of faction condition with paddy-paddy-secondary crops planting pattern, covered : 1) 350, 250, 60 ha; 2) 210, 150, 150 ha; 3) 210, 200, 100 ha; and 4) 332, 150, 38 ha. Water balance based on scenario is shown in Figure 3. From the fourth scenarios of planting intensity, the 3rd scenario is as a conducive choice.

Figure 3. Water balance based on the scenario

However, this alternative scenario is conducted as an adaptation step to the downhill environment condition related to scarcity water on the weir at the time. Adaptation also can be conducted with change of planting pattern if water availability annually continue downhillly for example paddy-paddy-secondary crops become paddy-secondary crops-secondary crops. But if planting pattern

of paddy-paddy-secondary crops will be maintained, while water availability remain to be drastic downhill hence require to be made a change of agricultural methods from conventional system to the system of rice intensification (SRI). Conventional irrigation systems need larger water for flooding, while SRI system tend to use water economically and do not need flooding.

CONCLUSIONS

Land use change in the upstream Ciliwung watershed has indentified by land conversion become building areas due to tourism growth. Land use change upstream Ciliwung watershed with Q_{max}/Q_{min} ratio = 171.39 > 120 is in critical category. Land use change in the upstream Ciliwung watershed causes discharge degradation in the middle areas like Cibanon irrigation area, so water availability for irrigation tend to downhill as a result of infiltration downhill that caused low of base flow.

As adaptation step to discharge availability in the Cibanon weir have been made 4 (four) scenarios. If water availability in the weir declines drastic, alternative of planting pattern and agricultural methods are required, for example by changing of conventional cultivation to system of rice intensification (SRI).

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Author thanks to Research Center for Water Resources, which have accommodation cost for taking part in in this seminar. Thank also to Dinas Sumber Daya Air, West Java Province, and to all colleagues in the Balai Litbang Lingkungan Keairan.

REFERENCES

- Arifin, H.S. 2011. Green city concept-ecologis city-sustainability city and implementation in Indonesia. Workshop Green City.
- BAPLAN (Badan Planologi Nasional). 2012. Map of the Ciliwung watershed land cover.
- DSDA (Dinas Sumber Daya Air). 2017. The weir discharge data on the West Java Province irrigation year 2017. Dinas Sumber Daya Air, Provinsi Jawa Barat.
- Lisnawati, Y., and A. Wibowo. 2010. Analysis of water discharge fluctuation due to land use change in Puncak Area, Bogor District. *Jurnal Penelitian Hutan Tanaman* 7(4): 221-226.

- Permenhut P/61. 2014. Peraturan Menteri Kehutanan Republik Indonesia No. P.61/Menhut-II/2014. Monitoring and evaluation of the watershed. Kementerian Kehutanan Republik Indonesia. Jakarta, Indonesia. 33 p.
- Pramono, A.A. 2010. The Land economic value change analysis of the people forest land conversion in the upstream Ciliwung watershed. *Jurnal Sylva Lestari* 4(3):11-20.
- Pratama, W., and S.B. Yuwono. 2016. The analysis of the land use change to hydrologic characteristic of Bulok watershed. *Jurnal Sylva Lestari* 4(3):11-20.
- Ruspendi, D., S. Hadi S., and O. Rusdiana. 2013. Study of land cover changing in Ciliwung upper stream with spatial dynamic approach. *Jurnal Lansekap Indonesia* 5(2):1-5.
- Swandayani, T.H. 2010. AHP Process in the vulnerability of societies value to climate change and adaptation base on forest ecosystem of the Ciliwung watershed. Thesis, IPB, Bogor.
- Wahyuni, S., and Syartinilia. 2015. Study of biodiversity value and distribution in the upper stream of Ciliwung watershed. *E-Jurnal Arsitektur Lansekap* 1(2):91-101.
- Wasis, B., B.H. Saharjo, H.S. Arifin, and A.N.N. Prasetyo. 2012. Land covers change and its impact to carbon stocks in Ciliwung watershed. *Jurnal Silvikultur Tropika* 3(2):108-113.